

CCTV – human factor challenges

John WOOD

CCD Design & Ergonomics Ltd, 11 – 21 Northdown Street, London N1 9BN, England

Abstract. CCTV technology advances raise new human factor challenges in the use and operation of these systems. Increasingly it's the operators' abilities which now must be fully considered if the full potential of a CCTV system is to be realised. This paper will present some core human factor considerations including, target size requirements, the impact of monitor numbers, image complexity and a taxonomy for CCTV tasks. Experiments will be described on the impact of different arrangements of images on a motorway detection task.

Keywords. Task types, target features, scene numbers, image presentation

1. Introduction

Whereas 20 years ago the use of CCTV was relatively limited it is now to be found offshore, in nuclear processing plants, for controlling motorways, monitoring city centres and an essential tool in security & surveillance systems. At present practical human factors advice struggles to keep up with the rapidly expanding range of applications.

Ergonomic factors which can be manipulated to maximise performance are illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig 1: Human Factor issues and CCTV System Operation

The range of CCTV based tasks is ever expanding as new uses are found for this technology. Some of these tasks involve general surveillance, such as monitoring a railway station for overall levels of crowding. Others tasks may require a specific target to be identified which may appear at infrequent and unpredictable times.

Video analytics and 'intelligent' CCTV systems will undoubtedly remove many of the

repetitive, more soporific tasks but there will remain a hard core for which the human operator must still remain responsible. It is to these remaining tasks that this paper is addressed.

2. CCTV Task Types

As with any other system the most appropriate CCTV interface can only be specified if the actual task which is to be carried out is understood. Human factors engineers need to be able to ensure the visual demands of the CCTV task lie within the known capabilities for human vision and information processing. Table 1 presents examples of CCTV task types. Task differences will have an influence on what is the most appropriate ergonomic solution.

Table 1: Sample CCTV Task Types

TASK TYPE	EXAMPLE
Detect static anomaly with a static background	Checking train doors are closed
Detect change in a static background	Person moving into sterile zone
Detect change of state with a static background	Motorway traffic
Moving with a changing background	Checking railway tracks
Diagnostic in static image	Speeding check against road markings
Control in a dynamic environment	Remote control
Detection of subtle changes of behaviour	Pickpockets in metro systems

3. Target Features

An individuals' ability to spot a target is influenced by such presentation features including:

- Target size
- Field of view
- Target movement
- Self-paced v paced image presentation
- Image numbers

- Frequency of events
- Performance demands
- Image complexity
- Target contrast against background

The importance of ‘image complexity’ is illustrated by the images below, Fig 2. Images may be inherently ‘simple’ in that the visual elements which make them up are limited – the view from a camera along a quiet road – or more complex in a busy city-centre road. Whilst most individuals find no great difficulty in sorting CCTV images into simple and complex the underlying reasons used are much more difficult to ascertain. Where images need to be closely monitored the levels of image complexity are likely to be important where high levels of detection performance are set.

Figure 2: Examples of Varying Image ‘Complexity’

Recent research, ref 1, has introduced the concept of a ‘scene’ to describe the content of CCTV images. A scene is a logical and meaningful set of visual information to be monitored with a specific aim. The example provided to illustrate this relates to road tunnel monitoring. The group of images used to monitor the flow in one direction would represent a ‘scene’. Were there to be an incident the detailed images selected would then become another scene. Whilst the work undertaken by the UK Home Office, ref 2, looked at target sizes in relation to individual monitors the same approach could be applied in relation to scenes. Figure 3 provides some general guidance on the size targets need to be in relation to operator tasks.

Figure 3: Target Image as a Varying Proportion of Scene Height

The impact of contrast can be seen in the example below where the same individual is walking across a floodlight railway level crossing at night and during the day, Fig 4. The figure on the nighttime image could easily be missed if the viewer did not have a cue from

the location in the daylight condition.

Fig 4: Contrast and ease of target detection.

4. Image Numbers

Many systems specifiers have not grasped the fact that increasing the number of cameras that a single operator has to view will have a cost in a decrease in target detection performance.

Research work has underlined the importance of monitor numbers in relation to operator performance at a detection task. Subjects were asked to watch a 10 minute video sequence under laboratory conditions looking at perfectly set up set of colour monitors. Ref 3. Changing the number of screens to be observed had a dramatic effect on detection performance, Table 2.

Table 2: Monitor numbers and detection performance

Monitor numbers	1	4	6	9
Accuracy scores %	85	74	58	53

Where simple monitoring - say of flows along a highway are required - a very large number of images can be viewed and the autocycling of some of these images can be acceptable. The task here will be to keep a general overview and respond when significant changes of state take place. Where intelligence led systems and video analytics are introduced the operator may be taken 'out of the loop' and only presented with images where an alert needs to be reconciled

5. Image Presentation

Where close scrutiny is required a single workstation mounted screen is likely to be the most appropriate solution. The general surveillance of a town centre will be more satisfactorily serviced by a video wall combined with a workstation screen.

The preferred number of sub-pictures on a single screen, for a motorway CCTV image task, was examined for the UK Highways Agency, ref 4. The task was to check that a 17 mile stretch of this emergency lane was clear of vehicles before allowing it to be used to ease traffic flows. The task involved checking over 170 CCTV images which had to be undertaken accurately and as quickly as possible. Image presentation could be either one at a time – which would take an unacceptably long time – or by the parallel presentation of

4 or 9 images: beyond this the sub-pictures became too small for reliably identifying a parked-up vehicle.

Subjects clearly preferred to check 1 or 4 images at a time – when 9 simultaneous images were presented error rates rose, Fig 5.

Figure 5: Checking Images with Lots of Movement

6. Image Size & Viewing Distances

There has been only limited amount of research, to date, on preferred viewing distances to monitors. Viewing distances for 14 inch and 21 inch monitors have been found to be 1 metre for the smaller monitor and 2.5 metres for the larger ones, ref 5 & 6. Performance deteriorated as viewing distances increased. The studies were based on small samples and must be treated as indicative only.

In many instances a combination of displays are used – a desk-mounted ‘spot monitor’ for close inspection, with a video wall for general surveillance. Where images which may be of interest are detected on video wall they can be ‘pulled down’ for closer scrutiny on the desk screen.

7. Image arrangement

Ergonomic principles should be applied to the arrangement of images on a video wall in order to minimise errors and facilitate searching. When designing the layout some of the following considerations should be applied:

- Avoid duplication of images
- Arrangements of images should mirror the geographic arrangement of cameras where possible

- Logical sequences, such as for cameras in a tunnels, should be reflected in the layout
- Use of blank monitors for attention getting

8. Environmental Factors

Particular difficulties arise when CCTV screens are used in an environment where ambient lighting is high – for example external security points at site entrances or in overground railway cabs.

Illumination levels in control rooms are usually in the range of 150 – 350 lux. For anyone that has tried to use a laptop outside in daylight it will come as no surprise that levels can be 15,000 – 20,000 lux or higher.

9. Boredom & Motivation

Maintaining operators' levels of concentration and avoiding boredom are significant challenges for those designing predominantly CCTV monitoring jobs. Multifunctional roles for operators are generally recommended where the operator is not required to continuously monitor CCTV. Operators attention tends to decrease significantly after 20 to 30 minutes of continuous operation.

Where the CCTV task is carried out in isolation, and little or no extra task stimulation is provided, operators tend to experience drowsiness and boredom. Extreme underload is typically indicated by increased errors, loss of attention, rising boredom and easier distraction.

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